

Which Transferable Skills do Students Acquire in PBL? Insights from the Industrial Engineering and Management Course

Inês Silva¹, Beatriz Silva¹, Marta Ribeiro¹, Violeta Carvalho^{2,3,4,5}, Cristina S. Rodrigues², Ângela Silva², Anabela Alves², Carina Pimentel², Rui M. Sousa², Senhorinha Teixeira²

¹ Department of Production and Systems, School of Engineering, University of Minho, Guimarães, Portugal

² ALGORITMI/LASI Research Center, School of Engineering, University of Minho, Guimarães, Portugal

³ Mechanical Engineering and Resource Sustainability Center (MEtRICs), University of Minho, Campus de Azurém, Guimarães, Portugal

⁴ Center for MicroElectromechanical Systems (CMEMS UMinho), University of Minho, Campus de Azurém, Guimarães, Portugal

⁵ LABBELS—Associate Laboratory, 4806-909 Braga/Guimarães, Portugal

Email: a104681@alunos.uminho.pt, a104680@alunos.uminho.pt, a104773@alunos.uminho.pt, violeta.carvalho@dps.uminho.pt, crodrigues@dps.uminho.pt, asilva@dps.uminho.pt, anabela@dps.uminho.pt, carina.pimentel@dps.uminho.pt, rms@dps.uminho.pt, st@dps.uminho.pt

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Abstract

Project-based learning (PBL) methodologies have been used for two decades in Industrial Engineering and Management (IEM) programs of the Department of Production and Systems of the School of Engineering at the University of Minho. During the bachelor program, the students are engaged in three major projects, one during each year. They are called Integrated Projects (IPs) because all of them integrate the Curricular Units of the semester and they run under the PBL methodology. Teachers enrolled in these projects believe that those IPs not only facilitate the development of the technical skills of the Project Supporting courses but also are the more suitable way of providing students with abilities to learn and apply this knowledge. Additionally, teamwork and solving real problems are aspects that will enhance student performance in future professional contexts. These so-called transferable skills can make a difference and contribute significantly to the success of IEM students. Different teachers from the three IPs previously evaluated the most frequently cited transferable skills and the extent to which these skills are considered in each IP. In the present work, a previous exploratory study (on teachers' perceptions about transferable skills acquisition) is updated exploring the students' feelings and perceptions of the acquisition of the considered set of transferable skills. A survey taken of the 3rd year students was used to identify the main aspects to be improved in each IP project of the 1st and 2nd year of the bachelor's degree. The results reveal a quite positive perception of the students regarding the development of transferable skills, but also pointed out some improvement opportunities.

Keywords: Project Based Learning; Students Perspective; Transferable Skills

1 Introduction

Project-based learning (PBL) has established itself over the past decades as an effective pedagogical methodology in higher education, especially in fields with a strong practical component such as Industrial Engineering and Management (IEM). In the context of the University of Minho, the use of PBL in the Integrated Projects (IP) of the IEM bachelor's degree program highlights a commitment to an educational approach that seeks not only to develop technical skills but also a broad set of transferable skills essential for the professional world.

These Integrated Projects, carried out each year of the bachelor's degree at the University of Minho, integrate the various curricular units of the corresponding semester, encouraging students to work in teams and solve real-world problems, thus promoting a more active learning experience. Studies such as those by Helle et al. (2006) and Alves et al. (2017) indicate that PBL facilitates the development of skills such as communication, critical thinking, time management, and the ability to work in interdisciplinary contexts, all highly valued in today's labour market.

The literature has reinforced the importance of acquiring transferable skills in engineering education. According to Prince & Felder (2006), these skills are crucial for graduates to adapt to dynamic and multidisciplinary work environments. Furthermore, the integration of real-world projects into the academic curriculum offers students a unique opportunity to apply theoretical knowledge in practical situations, increasing their motivation and promoting both personal and professional development (Lavado-Anguera et al., 2024).

However, while the benefits of PBL in fostering transferable skills are well documented, its implementation also presents notable challenges, particularly in collaborative dynamics. As highlighted by Hussein (2021), students often face difficulties in coordinating tasks, managing interpersonal conflicts, and maintaining equitable contributions within project teams. Addressing these issues is essential to ensure that the full potential of PBL in skill development is effectively realized.

Building on a previous exploratory study that evaluated the most frequently cited transferable skills by teachers involved in the IPs (Carvalho et al., 2024), the present work updates that analysis by incorporating third-year students' perceptions regarding the acquisition of these skills throughout the projects of the first and second years. A specific questionnaire was used to identify the main strengths and areas for improvement in each project, providing insights into the evolution of skill development along the academic path.

Thus, this paper is organized into four sections. The first is dedicated to the study context, describing the implementation of the Integrated Projects in the Industrial Engineering and Management program at the University of Minho and the importance of transferable skills. The second section presents the adopted methodology, including the characterization of the questionnaire and the profile of the participants. In the third section, the main results obtained are presented and discussed, focusing on students' perceptions of skill development throughout the projects. Finally, the fourth section presents the study's main conclusions, highlighting the identified areas for improvement and suggesting future directions for strengthening the acquisition of transferable skills within the academic journey.

2 Study Context

The integration of Project-Based Learning (PBL) at the University of Minho, within the Department of Production and Systems (DPS), dates back to the 2004/2005 academic year. At that time, Industrial Engineering and Management (IEM) students were introduced to an interdisciplinary project designed to provide a dynamic learning environment, where they could apply theoretical knowledge to real-world problems, developing both technical expertise and key transversal skills such as teamwork, problem-solving, and project management (Lima et al., 2007).

Since then, this approach to IEM education has evolved, but it was only formally incorporated into the curriculum in 2021. The introduction of the Integrated Project in Industrial Engineering and Management (IPIEM) as part of the course curricular structure marked a significant milestone, consisting of three separate curricular units (IPIEM I, II, and III), one for each year of the IEM undergraduate program. There, students combine the knowledge acquired in the remaining CUs of the respective semester, working in teams to solve complex, real-life challenges.

Thus, the core objectives of the IPIEM courses, besides enhancing students' technical skills by applying theoretical knowledge, is the development of soft skills such as teamwork, communication, and problem-solving, which are essential in their future professional environments. The initiative aims to create an immersive learning experience where students engage in hands-on activities, critical thinking, and collaborative work, simulating the challenges faced in the industry.

2.1 Integrated Project in Industrial Engineering and Management I

As the first integrated project, IPIEM I is situated in the first semester of the first year and incorporates a range of Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) subjects. More precisely, students begin their courses with Computer Programming I (CP I), Introduction to Economics Engineering (IEE), and Introduction to Industrial Engineering and Management (IEM), all of which are offered by the Engineering School. Additionally, subjects from the Science School, such as Calculus for Engineering (CE) and Linear Algebra for 3 Engineering (LA), are also taught this semester. These CUs come together in an integrated project (IPIEM I), which holds five European Credit Transfer System (ECTS), totalling 140 hours of student work.

By default, this PBL project focuses on sustainability. For the current third-year students of the IEM undergraduate degree, the theme of their first IPIEM (2022/2023 academic year) was to design a production system to value end-of-life clothes. As such, 68 freshman students were organized into eight teams of seven to nine members. The project was also carried out by a team coordinator, instructors from various courses, volunteer tutors (including department lecturers and third-year IEM students), and occasionally, volunteer educational researchers, making up a total of 17 team members for this specific edition.

Throughout the project, the teams' assessments were conducted at specific milestones, which included some deliverables to be presented, as illustrated in Table 1.

Table 1. Milestones, deliverables, and weight of each in the assessment methodology of IPIEM I (adapted from Alves et al. (2023)).

Milestone	Date	Deliverables	Weight
1	2022.09.28 (Week 2)	Pilot-project presentation (10'/team + 5' discussion)	Not assessed
2	2022.10.26 (Week 6)	Team progress (10'/team) + enlarged tutorial (15'/team)	7.5% (team) + not assessed
3	2022.11.15 (Week 9)	IEM@ProjectNetworking result (5'/pair)	10% (individual)
4	2022.12.09 (Week 12)	Preliminary report (40 pages maximum)	20%+5% (team)
5	2023.01.11 (Week 14)	Final report (50 pages maximum) + Prototypes	35% + 20% (team)
6	2023.01.16 (Week 15)	Final presentation and discussion (15'/team + 30' discussion) + blog	12.5% + 5% (team)

During the first week of classes (from September 19 to 23), IPIEM I is introduced to the freshman students, who arrived at the university one week before. In this session, a learning project guide, which outlines all the details of the PBL organization process, is presented by the coordination team. The guide includes the expected learning outcomes for each course, schedules, the role of the tutors, contacts, and other essential information.

By then, they are ready to develop teamwork skills and use web communication tools, such as blogs, to support the development and exposure of their work and ideas. By the following week, they are expected to present their findings in the pilot-project presentation, which includes their study of the theme, their team organization, and how they plan to manage the blog.

Students are then required to begin drafting a report about their work. While each course defines its specific tasks and content, the goal is to integrate most of this content into the project. Additionally, students receive training in teamwork, focusing on team formation, the use of tools to enhance collaboration, project management, and communication platforms, such as Padlet, Blog, and Asana.

As part of their deliverables, student teams are required to review a report submitted by another team. This paper explores the critical thinking developed by the students performing the peer review, by examining the feedback provided, the questionnaire, the technical checklist, and the results of the report content.

To promote effective teamwork, each student is required to conduct anonymous peer assessments, after completing some milestones. These evaluations are then reviewed in meetings with team members, guided by tutors to help resolve any conflicts that may arise.

More details about the implementation of this project can be found in Alves et al. (2023).

2.2 Integrated Project in Industrial Engineering and Management II

As the previous integrated project, IPIEM II was first implemented in the academic year of 2021/2022, during the second semester of the second year of the IEM undergraduate degree. Four CUs participated in this PBL: Complements of Applied Statistics (5 ECTS), Operational Research and Optimization (5 ECTS), Numerical Methods (5 ECTS), and Information Systems and Technology (5 ECTS).

With the knowledge acquired in these curricular units, students were expected to solve an industrial engineering problem using real data, by applying statistical data analysis techniques, as well as incorporating tools for database manipulation and management and implementing software solutions related to data processing and analysis.

In the previous 2023/2024 academic year, the objective of the project was to define an efficient supply chain system for a product from an industrial sector in the northern region of Portugal (e.g., textiles, footwear, electronics, cork, etc.).

To achieve this, nine teams (randomly formed with eight members each from the 72 total students attending the CU) had to contact companies that meet these requirements so they could provide the necessary datasets about their supply chain. With this approach, the aim was to provide second-year students with a comprehensive and integrated understanding of the engineering topic and its practical applications in the real world (Carvalho et al., 2024).

As more advanced students, they are expected to develop more autonomous work, so they have fewer checkpoints, as outlined in Table 2, as well as not having a student mentor, unlike in the previous project.

Table 2. Milestones, deliverables, and weight of each in the assessment methodology of IPIEM II.

Milestone	Date	Deliverables	Weight
1	2023.02.28	Poster presentation session (pitch) (5' per team)	10% (team)
2	2024.04.12	Preliminary report (maximum 20 pages)	20% (team)
3	2024.05.27	Final report (maximum 40 pages)	40% (team)
4	2024.05.29	Final presentation (12'/team) and discussion of the work (maximum 15'/team)	30% (team)

In addition to the group assessment, the individual evaluation takes into account a correction factor calculated through the peer evaluations conducted after each milestone.

2.3 Integrated Project in Industrial Engineering and Management III

As the final IPIEM, this integrated project takes place in the second semester of the third and final year of the IEM undergraduate degree. Following the same principles as in previous editions, it involves 5 CUs, specifically Data Analytics (5 ECTS), Decision Models (5 ECTS), Logistics and Supply Chain Management (5 ECTS), Manufacturing Planning and Control (5 ECTS), and Project Analysis in Industrial and Engineering Management (5 ECTS). In the academic year of 2024/2025, the coordination team consisted of five teachers, one representing

each CU, and the students were divided into 10 teams, each consisting of 7 members, who were randomly assigned.

The objective is for students to be able to develop a team project based on a case study related to the increased demand for three products from a wood furniture manufacturing company. As a result, the company must increase its production capacity to meet the new orders promptly, while maintaining product quality and minimizing production costs. The overarching challenge for each student team is to develop proposals and plans across various areas, including equipment and labour requirements, logistics, production planning and control, and information systems, all aimed at helping the company achieve its objectives (Carvalho et al., 2024). In addition to the technical skills associated with the CUs, the aim is to also develop transversal skills (communication, teamwork, leadership, etc.). The evaluation method is described in Table 3.

In addition to the team assessment, there is an individual correction factor, determined by the peer evaluation before each presentation. The grade is also increased by 1 point if students attend all seminars conducted throughout the semester.

Table 3. Milestones, deliverables and weight of each in the assessment methodology of IPIEM III.

Milestone	Date	Deliverables	Weight
1	2025.03.18	Intermediate Presentation/Discussion	15% (team)
2	2025.05.20	Final Presentation/Discussion	15% (team)
3	2025.05.20	Final report	70% (team)

3 Methodology

The present study is based on the analysis of responses to a questionnaire on transferable skills applied to third-year students of the Industrial Engineering and Management bachelor's degree at the University of Minho. The survey was specifically targeted at students involved in the Integrated Projects in Industrial Engineering and Management I, II, and III, with the aim of understanding, on one hand, the skills effectively developed in the first two projects, and on the other hand, the students' expectations regarding the skills they hope to acquire with the completion of IPIEM III, which is scheduled to conclude in May 2025. The data collection instrument was structured to cover a set of transferable skills considered essential for the future professional performance of the students, such as oral and written communication, teamwork ability, and complex problem-solving, among others. Thus, the questionnaire included closed-ended questions using Likert scales as well as open-ended questions, allowing students to share additional comments about their experiences in the projects. The sample analyzed consists of 35 students, from a total population of about 70 enrolled in the third year of the degree, corresponding to a response rate of 50%. This rate is considered satisfactory for exploratory studies of this nature and provides a solid basis for analyzing general trends in students' perceptions. It is important to highlight that the responses were collected anonymously, ensuring the confidentiality of participants' personal data and encouraging greater honesty and spontaneity in the answers provided.

3.1 Profile of the respondents

The analysis of the respondents' demographic characteristics indicates a clear predominance of female participants, representing 74.29% (n=26) of the sample, whereas male participants account for 25.71% (n=9). Concerning age distribution, the majority of respondents are 20 years old (54.29%), followed by 21-year-olds (37.14%), with smaller proportions aged 22 (5.71%) and 24 years (2.86%). The age distribution observed among the participants aligns with the expected demographic profile of third-year students enrolled in the Industrial Engineering and Management program.

4 Results

Students' assessment regarding the degree of development of a set of transferable skills across the three projects was conducted using a 5-point Likert scale, where 1 corresponds to "Very poorly developed" and 5 to "Highly developed". The data analysis, presented in Table 4, was based on the percentage of students who assigned scores of 4 or 5, corresponding to the categories "Well developed" and "Highly developed", to the various transferable skills addressed in the IPIEM I, II, and III projects. This method of analysis allows for a more precise observation of the degree of positive perception regarding the development of each skill, using the frequency of higher scores within the sample of 35 students as a central indicator. In parallel, these perceptions were compared with the qualitative evaluation provided by instructors in a study by Carvalho et al. (2024), expressed through the scale: ++: developed; +: somewhat developed; -: poorly developed; --: not developed. This external perspective complements the quantitative analysis and provides additional insights into the students' educational progress.

Table 4. Transferable skills identified in each project: students' perspective versus faculty's perspective (adapted from Carvalho et al. (2024)).

Transferable Skills	IPIEM I		IPIEM II		IPIEM III	
	Students	Teachers	Students	Teachers	Students	Teachers
	Well developed/ Highly developed	Perception	Well developed/ Highly developed	Perception	Well developed/ Highly developed	Perception
Identification of critical points for the work	77.1%	-	85.7%	++	85.7%	+
Creativity expression	80%	++	80%	+	80%	--
Logical reasoning ability	91.4%	-	88.6%	+	91.4%	+
Persistence	71.4%	+	91.4%	-	91.4%	--
Adaptability	88.6%	-	88.6%	-	91.4%	-
Autonomous learning	82.9%	+	85.7%	+	88.6%	++
Willingness to help colleagues	88.6%	-	91.4%	-	94.3%	+
Proactivity	85.7%	-	88.6%	+	88.6%	+
Attendance	82.9%	--	88.6%	+	88.6%	--
Meeting deadlines	94.3%	+	94.3%	++	94.3%	+
Respect for differences	91.4%	--	91.4%	-	88.6%	++
Collaboration with the group	88.6%	++	82.9%	+	94.3%	+
Ethics and professionalism	91.4%	--	88.6%	+	94.3%	--
Collective construction of solutions	85.7%	-	82.9%	-	91.4%	-
Stimulating collaboration	85.7%	+	82.9%	-	91.4%	+
Recognition of colleagues' contributions	85.7%	++	88.6%	-	91.4%	++
Written communication	71.4%	+	80%	++	85.7%	++
Assertiveness	82.9%	++	85.7%	+	94.3%	++
Ability to listen and understand others	91.4%	+	91.4%	-	94.3%	-
Public speaking	80%	++	91.4%	++	91.4%	++
Conflict mediation within the group	77.1%	-	82.9%	-	82.9%	-
Learning based on recognizing one's own mistakes	88.6%	-	85.7%	+	85.7%	-
Openness to receiving criticism and feedback	85.7%	-	91.4%	+	91.4%	+

It's important to emphasize, however, that there is a fundamental distinction between the nature of the responses related to each project: while the evaluations for IPIEM I and II reflect students' retrospective perceptions of skills already developed, the responses regarding IPIEM III relate to students' expectations about the skills they hope to acquire. This distinction has implications for data interpretation, as a high rating for a skill in IPIEM III can reflect students' confidence or aspirations, rather than a confirmed outcome.

Overall, students demonstrate a strong appreciation for the development of transferable skills across the three projects. In several dimensions, the percentage of responses in the top categories exceeds 80%, indicating a broadly positive perception. Skills such as "Logical reasoning ability", "Meeting deadlines", and "Assertive communication" reach values between 91% and 94%, suggesting that students perceive that all integrated projects helped them develop these skills.

However, when compared with the evaluations provided by instructors, some discrepancies emerge that warrant attention, as certain skills are assessed more critically by teachers. For instance, "Adaptability" receives over 88% positive responses from students across all projects, yet it is consistently rated with a "-" by instructors. This may indicate a divergence in how this skill is perceived by the two groups. A similar situation is observed with the skill "Ethics and professionalism", which, despite receiving a high student rating (91.4%), is given the lowest possible rating ("-") in IPIEM III. This contrast may reflect a misalignment between students' expectations and instructors' perceptions of the challenges involved in developing this competence, particularly in the context of more complex or professionally oriented project environments.

In contrast, for the skill "Group collaboration", there is a clear convergence between students' perception (with over 85% of responses in the top categories) and the instructors' evaluation, which ranges from "+" to "++" in different projects. This alignment suggests that collaborative dynamics have been effectively encouraged and acknowledged by both sides.

"Creativity expression", while positively rated by students with percentages close to 80%, shows a declining trend in teacher evaluations over the course of the projects, dropping from "++" in IPIEM I to "-" in IPIEM III. This discrepancy may stem from differing perspectives: students, drawing on their experiences in the first two projects, may expect to continue developing creativity in IPIEM III; whereas instructors, based on their familiarity with the structure and demands of the third project, anticipate a reduced emphasis on creative expression due to its stronger focus on technical execution and task completion.

Other skills, such as "Meeting deadlines", are rated highly by both students and instructors. Interestingly, however, this competence still appears in the open-ended responses as an area for improvement, suggesting that positive quantitative ratings may not fully capture individual difficulties or varying experiences within the group.

These qualitative comments, which allowed students to freely identify the competencies they perceived as less developed during each of the project phases, are limited in number (three per project), but responses reveal consistent and recurring patterns throughout the academic journey, highlighting aspects that may be underrepresented or generalized in the quantitative analysis.

The most frequently mentioned competency was time management, identified as a recurring challenge in the first two project editions and anticipated as a potential difficulty in the third. This observation is particularly noteworthy given that, in the Likert-scale analysis, the competency of "Meeting deadlines" was among the highest rated by both students and instructors. This apparent contradiction may reflect a distinction between group performance and individual self-perception, suggesting that although teams were generally able to meet deadlines, many students acknowledged weaknesses in their personal ability to organize and plan their time.

Proactivity was also identified as an area for improvement at various stages of the project. The repeated mention of this skill at different moments in the academic path indicates a growing awareness among students of its importance, particularly its connection to initiative, responsibility, and autonomy within the context of teamwork. Although proactivity received reasonably positive percentages in the quantitative analysis, its absence among the top-rated competencies reinforces the significance of this qualitative evidence.

Another theme that emerged from the open-ended responses was the need for stronger alignment between the projects and the professional world. Students expressed a desire for a more direct connection with real business contexts, including the integration of practical challenges, case studies, or mentoring opportunities with industry professionals. This suggestion highlights the pedagogical value of realism in learning experiences and may be interpreted as a call for a partial reconfiguration of the projects to foster closer alignment with the demands and dynamics of the labour market.

5 Conclusions

The overall analysis of the collected data highlights the positive impact of the IPIEM on the development of transferable skills throughout the course. While students show optimism and confidence, particularly regarding the anticipated outcomes of IPIEM III, faculty feedback provides a grounded and sometimes more critical perspective. Recognizing the difference between experienced skill development in the earlier projects and expectations for the final project is essential for accurately understanding and acting upon these results. This nuanced view offers valuable guidance for enhancing future iterations of the program.

The discrepancy between students' self-perception and faculty assessment, especially in skills such as "Ethics and Professionalism" and "Adaptability," underscores the need to promote feedback moments throughout the entire educational process. Similarly, the qualitative contributions from students reinforce the need to develop skills such as time management and proactivity, which are frequently referred to as challenges, despite being well-rated quantitatively in the questionnaire.

In this context, the IPIEM projects stand out as key elements in the implementation of a PBL approach, providing realistic formative experiences focused on solving real-world problems and team collaboration. However, suggestions for a closer alignment with the professional world point to the potential for the evolution of this model, emphasizing the relevance of integrating business contexts and mentorship practices.

Thus, this research contributes to strengthening an approach of self-assessment and continuous improvement, serving as a valuable resource for the refinement of future pedagogical strategies. The continued data collection in the upcoming academic years will allow for monitoring the impact of integrated projects on the development of essential skills for entering the job market.

References

- Alves, A. C., Leão, C. P., Abreu, M. F., Pimentel, C., Malheiro, M. T., Oliveira, S., Ramos, M. P., & Oliveira, J. M. (2023, October 29). Stimulating Critical Thinking Through Report Peer-Review in a Project-Based Learning by Engineering Freshman Students. Volume 8: Engineering Education. <https://doi.org/10.1115/IMECE2023-112542>
- Alves, A. C., Leão, C. P., Moreira, F., & Teixeira, S. (2017). Project-Based Learning and its Effects on Freshmen Social Skills in an Engineering Program. In *Human Capital and Competences in Project Management*. InTech. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.72054>
- Carvalho, V., Rodrigues, C. S., Teixeira, S., Silva, Â., Sousa, R. M., Costa, L., Alves, A., & Pimentel, C. (2024). Transferable Skills Development through Project-Based Learning in an Industrial Engineering and Management Degree. PAEE/ALE'2024 International Conference on Active Learning in Engineering Education, 451–460. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14062853>
- Helle, L., Tynjälä, P., & Olkinuora, E. (2006). Project-Based Learning in Post-Secondary Education – Theory, Practice and Rubber Sling Shots. *Higher Education*, 51(2), 287–314. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-004-6386-5>
- Hussein, B. (2021). Addressing Collaboration Challenges in Project-Based Learning: The Student's Perspective. *Education Sciences*, 11(8), 434. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11080434>

- Lavado-Anguera, S., Velasco-Quintana, P.-J., & Terrón-López, M.-J. (2024). Project-Based Learning (PBL) as an Experiential Pedagogical Methodology in Engineering Education: A Review of the Literature. *Education Sciences*, 14(6), 617. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci14060617>
- Lima, R. M., Carvalho, D., Assunção Flores, M., & Van Hattum-Janssen, N. (2007). A case study on project led education in engineering: students' and teachers' perceptions. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 32(3), 337–347. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043790701278599>
- Prince, M. J., & Felder, R. M. (2006). Inductive Teaching and Learning Methods: Definitions, Comparisons, and Research Bases. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 95(2), 123–138. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2168-9830.2006.tb00884.x>